

Endorsing Cognizance about Traditional Patterns of Pakistan in Truck Art through Fashion Design for the Global Market

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Abstract

In this article, we hope to explore and explore the uniqueness and uniqueness of common trucking topics and examples in Pakistan. Truck work is one of the most popular artistic activities in Pakistan, energetic and lively. The beautifully exuberant designs in multi-colored palettes create something vibrant and sophisticated that reflects the diversity of Pakistani culture. Truck builders are in their own reality, performing and communicating their work with their own passion and instinct. Advocating and raising awareness about the impact of traditional themes and examples is to present an idea that will take truck art off the streets and integrate it into lifestyle, especially in age Y. This idea will also help the general population improve their knowledge, understand and appreciate the value of traditional Pakistani themes and examples. The main goal of the modern craftsman and architect in any case is to be motivated to spread and present the living message of this artistic expression locally and throughout the planet. By integrating and applying truck components, know-how in the selection of materials and styles will also contribute to the development and improvement of traditional works of art. In addition, the article will also explore various designs that can help enhance the artistic expression of the truck, such as its batik style delivery. Attentiveness and understanding of the creativity and display of truck craftsmanship will protect the familiar social identities of the coming era of artisans, designers and truck manufacturing specialists of Pakistan. This work will also help spread the true essence of the Pakistani way of life, nation and people.

Keywords: *Pakistan, Textile Design, Fashion Design, Textile Industry, Contemporary Design, Young Generation, Patterns, Surface Design, Cultural Identity, Global Market, New Media, Truck Art, Economy, Traditional Patterns, Social Uplift.*

INTRODUCTION

This part will explore traditional themes and examples in Pakistan and their application in the material and style industry, as well as other surface plans such as truck manufacturing. Having themes and examples is a fundamental part of improving Pakistan's culture and economy. This project paper aims to explore the heterogeneous culture of the regions of Punjab, Sindh, Balochistan, Pashtun and Kashmir, which have their own striking and attractive interactions with the ground planes of Pakistan, especially in manufacturing, materials and truck design. Pakistan is a South Asian country known for its strong zones and rich multicultural base that has developed over 5000 years. Pakistani dishes have their roots in a rich and dynamic past. Pakistan Materials Industry is the most developed and largest industry of Pakistan. Thanks to a more developed industry, this specialty is now fast paced and demanding, Pakistani style is extremely elegant and casual, but some old traditional methods are used locally and globally. This project will also explore and create synergy using themes and examples in contemporary material and stylistically. A theme is a component of the iconography of a particular theme or type of theme that appears in a work or that may frame a major theme. over the previous hundreds of years, on every surface. Themes are a rich outline for example, a specific component, or a dominant idea in a figurative or academic structure. Themes and examples are an important part of every ancient culture. Themes can have a deep impact and connection to each culture. Topics are treated as examples of units. Themes are reproduced and organized into various examples for ideal impact, such as redundancy, rhythm and degree.

Figure 1.1: Motif: Jasmin Flower (Pakistan National Flower)

In art, a motif is a recurring idea, motif, image, or theme. In fiber art, a pattern (also called a block or square) is a smaller element in a much larger work. Topics can be any size, but usually in some odd jobs all topics are the same size. The examples and combinations used in a theme can vary greatly, but there is usually an element that unites them, such as a surface, a line pattern, or a pattern that gives the finished product a more elegant appeal. An example is the peculiar theme of repeating events or elements, sometimes called components of a set. These components are repeated in advance. It is usually a drawing or image that can be used to create things or parts of things, especially if the things created have had enough practice to produce a hidden example, in which case the things speak. set an exceptional example. The most significant examples are regarding repetition and periodicity. In materials, printing is the use of varied textures in unmistakable patterns or engraving planes. In properly printed textures, the variety is bonded to the fiber to resist washing and erosion. However, printing a material is associated with coloring, while with legal coloring the entire texture is systematically covered with one tone, and when printing at least one tone is applied only to individual parts and in pronounced patterns.

Figure 1.2: Pattern created by repetition

Extremely old themes used creatively across industries. In the past, the primary subject of a creative work, such as a canvas, was a specific person, a collection, a moment in history, or part of a life-giving work of art, such as a composition on canvas. vessel. due to correspondence. . Every culture is made up of themes and patterns, we can trace the theme of creatures in Byzantine crafts made from silk and other ancient materials.

Many frames in Islamic culture represent themes, including images of the sun, moon, creatures such as ponies and lions, flowers and scenes; A mathematical example is a kind of boxed example of mathematical figures. Components will be pieces or parts that can be divided and characterized in any visual plane or bright element. They make up the design of a piece and can convey a wide variety of messages. In this article he included point or trace, line, shape, structure, space, variety and surface.

Standards are ideas used to coordinate or organize the major components of a plan. Again, the way these standards are applied affects the expressive essence or message of the work. The standards are Balance, Expansion, Rhythm, Accent and Solidarity.

A design is a set of components or themes that are repeated in advance to ensure the ideal impact or goal. Design is one of the super visual components used in the style and materials industry (along with variety, structure, line and surface) to create an attractive design.

A visual game plan of topics and examples in a given space is called a visual plan. A visual plan is the use of symbolism, variety, shapes, typography and structure to enhance comfort and further develop the customer experience. The visual plane as a field has surpassed both the user interface plane and visual presentation.

In crafting and designing, visual enhancements or themes can be collected and repeated to form a design intended to influence the viewer. Today, common themes and examples participate in other lives as examples of the modern

imaginative world, while maintaining their social value. From a planner's perspective, themes and examples are the cornerstone of any site plan, and they can also be combined to create beautiful plans.

The materials industry in Pakistan is one of the oldest and largest assembly industries in the country. Other major companies are agricultural companies that produce crops such as cotton, wheat, rice and sugarcane. The materials sector in Pakistan is one of the largest assembly industries in Pakistan. Pakistan is the eighth largest exporter of wealth in Asia. This area contributes 8.5% of the gross domestic product (Wikipedia). In addition, the region employs about 45% of the country's absolute labor force (and 38% of assemblers).

Figure 1.3: Textile Factory in Pakistan

Figure 1.4: Agricultural activities

Pakistan is the fourth largest producer of cotton with the third largest turnover in Asia after China and India and accounts for 5% of global turnover. Currently, there are 1,221 cotton gins, 442 lathes, 124 huge lathes and 425 small material production units (Wikipedia).

In Pakistan, materials are transformed by rolling, weaving, sewing, crocheting or felting. Material also refers to any material formed by joining threads. Texture refers to any material produced by rolling, sewing, stretching, knitting or holding that can be used for additional products or clothing.

Figure 1.5: Fabric production

Today we find ancient weaving techniques and colored cottons that are still used in industry today. Tie and color, engraving and weaving is a type of ornamentation that is the most extravagant method of conveying feelings and style using color, wax, variety, needle and thread in texture.

Figure 1.6: Embroidery

Rural areas also produce hand-woven fabrics with beautiful designs. Batik, tie-dye and block printing are textile techniques that still exist in many countries.

These surface designs are then developed into designs or decorative arts, which can usually be broken down into a number of different elements that can be called patterns.

Figure 1.7: Ornamental or decorative arts

The surface plan includes the shading, placement and organization of fibers and textures. This includes inventive exploration of cycles such as coloring, drawing, printing, sewing, decorating, sewing, rolling, knitting, felting and paper making. Surface flatness is any strategy that controls or modifies the outer layer of texture. This includes making art, painting, printing, stenciling, contrasting, sewing, decorating (like adding brush strokes), gluing, rolling, etc. They can be used in material work, engineering, enrichment, or visual themes. Then, at this stage, they can be assembled and repeated to form a design intended to have a significant impact on the viewer.

Figure 1.8: Surface design

The topic and examples are increasingly used in the materials industry. The variation of traditional themes and examples aims to create creative textural plans that could occupy an exceptional place in the field of materials. A material plane is a plane drawn onto a texture. This is an elegant and improved texture property. It reflects the experience and art as well as the practice or culture of the user. Filled with ingenuity and gifted with vast horizons, materials planning is a complex and evolving field. Over time, material creators around the world became motivated to refine their textures. Today's new procedures are advancing the materials industry and textures, themes and patterns are now becoming more refined and refined to compete globally in the fashion industry.

Well known printing process used in Pakistan such as wood blocks, stencils, engraved plates, roll or screen printing, hand block printing, copper plate engraving printing, hand printing roller, camera or machine, screen printing, screen printing, computerized material. seal. Traditional weaving and other handicraft processes such as ajrak, chunri and batik are used in Pakistan.

CONCLUSION

The result of a research and project aimed at understanding new advances in materials and design in Pakistan. Promote and promote understanding of topics and examples in the truck manufacturing industry. Notice, acknowledge and encourage the use of themes and examples in truck work within the current material and style plan. Directly and indirectly, this will make the work of the cargo handler easier.

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